

Declaration of the granting of rights of use

Name _____

Christian Name _____

Address _____

Date of Birth _____

It is intended that Ms. / Mr. _____ (hereinafter: the undersigned) will create his / her student [project work / thesis / ...] within the framework of the current project [name of the project].

In this context, it is necessary that the work results of the above project of the University of Hildesheim Foundation, of the signatory [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim Foundation and the project partners involved are available.

Letter of acceptance

I agree that my work results created in the project above in the form of texts, files, tables, graphics, overviews etc. can be used for the project and also for other purposes and in particular may also be used for publications. For this purpose, I grant [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim an irrevocable, exclusive, transferable, spatial, temporal and content-free right of use to use the work results I have developed free of charge for all types of use currently and in the future. A publication and further processing or modification of the work results by [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim Foundation or third parties to whom [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim Foundation assigns a right of use is explicitly approved.

§ 37 Copyright law does not apply.¹

I assure that I am not aware that the work results that I have created are neither wholly or partially encumbered with copyrights or other rights of third parties. If I become aware of conflicting third-party rights, I will inform [the institute / ...] of the Hildesheim University Foundation immediately. I shall indemnify [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim Foundation and third parties who [the institute / ...] of the University of Hildesheim Foundation have a right to use the work results from any claims for damages made by third parties in this connection.

I have made a conscious decision to write my [project work / final thesis / ...] as part of this project. In the run-up to the issue of topics, I was explicitly advised that I could also work on another topic that was not associated with the obligation to grant comprehensive rights of use.

All changes and additions to this declaration of commitment must be made in writing in order to be effective. This formal requirement can only be waived in writing.

Place, Date

Signature

¹ § 37 Copyright law: contracts for the granting of rights of use

(1) If the author grants someone else a right to use the work, in case of doubt he has the right to consent to the publication or use of a further processing of the work.

(2) If the author grants another right of use to reproduce the work, in case of doubt he has the right to transfer the work to image or sound carriers.

(3) If the author grants someone else the right to use the work in public, he is not entitled, in doubt, to make the work outside the event for which it is intended publicly perceivable by screen, loudspeaker or similar technical equipment.